

Isolation and Identification of Pathogenic Cause of Mold Grape Fruits and Evaluation of Effectiveness of Arabic Gum and Frankincense Inhibition of the Infection of Mold Grape Fruits

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Abstract:

The research was conducted at the laboratories of the College of Agriculture, at Karbala University. The main aim of this study was to identify and isolate fungi for grape rot and spoilage seen in marketplaces and storage facilities. Additionally the researchers examined the pathogenicity of these fungi testing concentrations of gum Arabic and frankincense to see their impact on grape rot causing fungi. The results of isolation and diagnosis revealed the presence of the fungal species *Fusarium*(T2), *Aspergillus*(T4), *Geotrichum*(T1), *Populaspota*(T3), and *Phytophthora*(T5) in all areas from which samples were collected, including Al-Hindiya, Al-Husseiniya, and Al-Khayrat.

The results showed that all tested isolates caused a significant increase in the percentage severity of infection under laboratory conditions. The fungi *Fusarium* and *Aspergillus* showed the highest percentage severity of infection, reaching 82% and 80%, respectively, followed by *Geotrichum* with a percentage severity of 75%, compared to other treatments and the control treatment, which had a percentage severity of 0.00%. The results also noted that most treatments significantly affected the growth of fungal isolates on the PDA culture medium. The percentage inhibition fungal growth of (T5) was highest 44.44% with treatment of 15% concentration of frankincense and gum Arabic separately follow by (T4) treated with 15% concentration of frankincense and (T1) treated with 15% concentration of gum Arabic. In contrast, the lowest inhibition fungal growth of fungi was 14.30% for (T3) and (T2, T3) treated with frankincense and gum Arabic respectively compared with other treatments.

Keywords: Grape Rot Fungi, Pathogenicity, Arabic Gum, Frankincense, Growth Rate.

Introduction

The grapevine is a summer fruit tree favored by many due to its pleasant taste and high content of vitamins and essential nutrients that boost the immune system and overall health (Sassos, 2021). Grapes face numerous issues leading to economic losses, such as reduced yield and quality. Among the most significant problems are the infestation of foliage and fruits by various agricultural pests, including insect pests and

pathogens, with fungal diseases being prominent (Padol, P. B., & Yadav, A. A., 2016, June). These issues accompany grapes in fields and storage, causing significant damage and yield loss. Key fungi that inflict severe damage on grape fruits, through parasitism and secretion of toxic substances harmful to consumer health, include *Aspergillus*, *Phytophthora*, *Alternaria*, *Geotrichum*, *Populaspota*, *Fusarium*, and *Cladosporium* (Hight & Nair, 1995; Jampagi & Kambrear, 2023).

Fungicides have been used to protect grape fruits from fungal diseases and have achieved good results in the field and storage. However, due to the harmful effects of fungicides and the impact of their residues on disrupting the natural balance of the environment, specialists in plant protection have sought alternative methods to combat these diseases. Biological control has been used as an alternative to fungicides for resisting pathogens and has succeeded in controlling decay diseases, but its effectiveness in disease management is closely linked to environmental conditions (Zhang, H., et al., 2020).

There is a new trend among specialists to test many environmentally friendly materials as alternatives to chemical substances, aiming to be safe for the environment and the health of humans and animals. Among these materials are plant extracts (Hernández-Ceja, A., et al., 2021). Some plants contain active substances against pathogens, and among these plants is frankincense. The extract of frankincense has been shown to reduce chocolate spot disease in bean plants in the greenhouse (El-Nagar, T. S., et al., 2022). Previous studies have also demonstrated the inhibitory potential of the alcohol extract of frankincense against several plant pathogens, including *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Alternaria sp.*, and *Penicillium* (Al-Edani, A. J. M., & Hussein, S. F., 2021). Other studies have indicated that using ethanol extract of propolis (bee glue) combined with Arabic gum reduced the growth of anthracnose fungus on papaya fruit during storage and preserved the quality of the fruit (Cheong, & Zahid, 2014).

Materials and Methods

Isolation and Identification of Fungi Associated with Grape Fruits

Grape seed samples were collected on 15/10/2022 from local markets and street vendors, which covered several areas of Karbala Governorate (Al-Husseinia Governorate, Al-Hindiya Governorate, and Al-Khairat Governorate). and storage area) were brought to the plant pathology laboratory and kept

refrigerated until the isolation procedure was performed in the following days.

The samples were washed with running water and then sterilized with 70% ethanol. The fruits were then cut into small pieces of 0.5 to 1 cm in diameter, all in the isolation chamber. PDA (potato dextrose agar) culture medium was prepared by placing 39 g of medium in a glass Erlenmeyer flask, placed in a water bath to ensure good mixing of the product. The lid of the flask was covered with a thick cotton plug and covered with a piece of silicone. The culture medium was transferred to a sterile chamber and cooled to 45°C. Sterile plastic plates were prepared, the cotton plug was removed near the flame, the flask cap was sterilized before pouring 15-20 ml culture medium into each plate leaving the plates solid and then stored in the refrigerator for consumption role in the future.

The grape fruit pieces were sterilized with 70% ethanol for 3, 5, and 7 seconds, then rinsed with sterile distilled water, and dried with sterile filter paper. The plant pieces were then planted, with four pieces per plate and ten plates per sample. The plates were sealed in sterile polyethylene bags and transferred to an incubator at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for three days. Afterward, the growing fungi were identified, and the purification process was carried out using the hyphal tip method. The fungi were incubated for seven days and then identified to the species level based on the characteristics described by Parmeter and Whitney (1970), which include colony color, the nature of the new hyphal branching, the shape of the conidiophore and conidia, the method of conidial production, and the shape of the sporulating structure.

Preservation of Fungal Isolates

The fungal isolates were preserved by preparing PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar) solution and dispensed in test tubes of 10 ml capacity each. The tip of the tube was wrapped with medical cotton and a piece of silicone was inserted. The tubes were then sterilized in an autoclave at 121 °C and 15 psi pressure. After sterilization, the tubes were placed upside down and left solid. They were then transferred to an isolation chamber, where purified fungi were inoculated,

and pieces of each fungus were placed in a cage in each cage kept at ± 25 °C and left in an incubator insert for 7 days.

Testing Pathogenicity

This experiment was performed in the Plant Pathology Laboratory. The grapes were prepared and washed under running water, then treated with 70% ethanol. The fruits were then cut with a sterile sharp blade, and pieces of previously purified fungi were placed into each cut, with one piece per cut. Three replicates were used for each fungal isolate in this experiment.

$$\text{Disease severity \%} = \frac{(\text{no. plants at } 0 \times 0) + (\text{no. plants at } 1 \times 1) \dots + (\text{no. plants at } 4 \times 4)}{(\text{no. plants tested}) \times 4} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Testing the Effect of Arabic Gum and Frankincense on the Growth of Fungal Isolates

This experiment was conducted in the Plant Pathology Laboratory. Concentration of the two substances mentioned above (15%) was prepared and added to the PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar) medium. The medium was then poured into plates and left to solidify. Simultaneously, fungal isolates were activated on PDA medium and incubated. After 7 days of

All procedures were performed in a sterile isolation room. After 7 days, the results were recorded by calculating the percentage of disease severity according to the following disease index:

0 - Healthy fruits
1 - Surface rot with a light color
2 - Rot extending to the lower layer with a dark color
3 - Deep rot with a dark color and fungal mycelium
4 - Complete fruit rot

And the percentage of severity of injury was calculated according to the equation (Mckinney, 1923).

incubation, a 0.5 cm diameter disc from each fungal isolate was inoculated into the pre-prepared plates containing the specified concentrations of Arabic gum and frankincense. The results were recorded after 7 days by calculating the percent inhibition. The concentrations of Arabic gum and frankincense growth fungal cultivars were compared with those of control (fungi only) (Katon & Gamliel, 1993). The percentage inhibition of fungi was calculated using the following method of the account.

$$\text{Inhibition \%} = \frac{\text{average diameter of fungus in control} - \text{average diameter of fungus in treatment}}{\text{average diameter of fungus in control}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Results and Discussion

Isolation and Diagnosis

The results of isolation and analysis revealed the presence of fungal species in all the sampled sites, including *Fusarium*, *Geotrichum*, *Populasporea*, *Phytophthora*, and *Aspergillus* (Figure 1) indicating that these fungi this is widespread across the sampling sites and

locations. In addition, the ability to produce and parasitize fruit species, including grapes, was evident. These fungi are known for their secretion of enzymes that break down tissues and fruit cells to obtain necessary nutrients. Once a parasitized fruit is consumed, the fungi may transfer to new fruits to parasitize them again, especially if there are wounds or scratches accompanying the grapes (Mikursoda *et al.*, 2013; Zoffoli *et al.*, 2009; Castiglion *et al.*, 2020).

**Figure 1. Microscopic images of the isolated fungal species, representing
 A- *Geotrichum* fungus; B- *Fusarium* fungus; C- *Populasporea* fungus;
 D- *Phytophthora* fungus; E- *Aspergillus***

Pathogenicity Testing of Isolated Pathogenic Fungi from Grape Fruits

The results (Table 1) indicated that all tested isolates caused a significant increase in the percentage of infection severity under laboratory conditions. *Fusarium* fungus notably impacted the percentage of infection severity, reaching

82% (Figure 2). This was followed by *Aspergillus* and *Geotrichum* fungi, with infection severity percentages of 80% and 75% respectively. The remaining treatments ranged between 67% and 70% in terms of infection severity percentage compared to the control, which had 0% infection severity. This variation can be

attributed to the fungi's differing abilities to produce various secondary metabolites and active compounds, notably enzymes that degrade and invade fruit tissues. Additionally, the negative effects caused by secondary metabolism compounds align with findings by several researchers, who have demonstrated variations among fungal species in their ability to parasitize their plant hosts (Thynne et al., 2017).

Table 1. Shows the Severity of Grape Rot Disease Caused by Fungal Isolates

ID	Treatment name	Severity (%)
1	Control	0.0
2	T1	75
3	T2	82
4	T3	70
5	T4	80
6	T5	67
LSD 0.05 =		2.40

Figure 2. The Damage Caused by Fungal Isolates on Grape Fruits

Inhibitory Capacity of Frankincense Against Fungal Isolates Associated with Grape Fruits under Laboratory Conditions

The results (Table 2) showed that the treatment with frankincense at a concentration of 15% affected the growth of all fungal isolates on PDA medium. Using frankincense at a concentration of 15% with fungi T5 and T4 gave the highest inhibition percentage (44.44, 42.90) compared to the other fungi. Meanwhile, the lowest inhibition rate was observed when using frankincense at a concentration of 15% with fungus T3. The reason for inhibiting the growth of fungal isolates in the presence of frankincense is due to

the presence of active compounds in this substance that work to inhibit fungal growth, and the amount depends on the type of fungus and the concentration used (Kredics, 2003).

Table 2. The Inhibitory Capacity of Frankincense Against Fungal Isolates

ID	Frankincense concentration with pathogenic fungi: 15%	The percentage of inhibition
1	T1+L	37.50
2	T2+L	28.60
3	T3+L	14.30
4	T4+L	42.90
5	T5+L	44.44
LSD 0.05 =		1.45

Inhibitory Capacity of Arabic Gum Against Fungal Isolates Accompanying Grape Fruits under Laboratory Conditions

The results (Table 3) showed that most treatments affected the growth of fungal isolates on PDA medium. The treatment of Arabic gum at a concentration of 15% with fungus T5 exhibited the highest inhibition rate, reaching 44.44%, compared to other fungi. This was followed by the treatment of Arabic gum at 15% with fungus T1, with an inhibition rate of 37.50%. The lowest inhibition rate was observed when 15% Arabica gum was used with fungi T2 and T3. The reason for this restriction is that the effective chemical composition of this ingredient acting to inhibit fungal growth, the extent to which this ingredient is effective depends on the type of fungus targeted.

Table 3. The Inhibitory Capacity of Arabic Gum Against Fungal Isolates

ID	Frankincense concentration with pathogenic fungi: 15%	The percentage of inhibition
1	T1+G	37.50
2	T2+G	14.30
3	T3+G	14.30
4	T4+G	28.60
5	T5+G	44.44
LSD 0.05 =		1.40

Conclusion

Conclusively, the pathogenic causes of grape rot were isolated, and pathogenicity was studied with each fungus. The study assessed the efficacy of Arabic gum and frankincense extract as the inhibitory action against the fungi causing grape rot. The results indicated that all the fungi isolated from grapefruits caused a significant increase in the percentage of infection severity under laboratory conditions. The results also illustrated that the other treatment and control gave the maximum percentage of severity with the fungi *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium*. Further, the results revealed that frankincense and Arabic gum reduced the rate of infection severity of all the fungi in relation to the control. Treatment, T5 with Arabic gum and frankincense separately gave the highest rate of inhibition for the fungi compared to the other fungi. The inhibition percentage was highest in the ones treated with frankincense and Arabic gum extract in those of T3, T2, and T3, respectively among them.

Recommendations

Use of Arabic gum and mastic gum as control agents for grape rot. There is also a need to develop compound materials using these two components to protect grapes from damage caused by pathogenic fungi and to investigate new effective compounds for the protection of the fruit and not degrade in an environmentally friendly manner.

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